

EVALUATION DESIGN & IMPLEMENTATION

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of the **Cut All Ties project** is to tackle gender-based violence through the design, implementation, and validation of an **effective and innovative training and ICT gamification** program to **disseminate** awareness-raising messages to **prevent and reduce gender-based violence (GBV) among 15 to 17 year olds** at high schools in **Spain** (Barcelona and Madrid) and **Italy** (Milan). The focus is on **changing the attitudes and behaviors of adolescents** within the paradigm of GBV.

The goal of the **Impact Evaluation** of the project is to detect the **effectiveness of student and teacher training and of the Social Coin gamification** for changing social norms. It also intends to **evaluate the potential impact of the program on opinions, perceptions, awareness, and behaviors with regard to sexual and gender related violence** in pupils that were not directly implicated in the program (same age schoolmates).

It is important to note, however, that, as explained and justified by the **project coordinators** in the **Process Evaluation Report**, different circumstances led to the **modification of the planned training, gamification and data gathering activities**. Consequently, **not all of the methodological recommendations** included in the evaluation design document **have been applied**.

The **Impact Evaluation Team** (hereinafter, IET) had to **reduce the initial objectives** and **simplify the data analysis**. We also warn that **the results should be read with caution** because of the diversity in terms of schools and the **sample** and due to the different **time-frames** and **methods of implementation**.

In this document we will present the evaluation plan and the implementation details.

EVALUATION PLAN

1. Planned methodological design

As its first step, the IET **adapted the original evaluation design** to make it more **coherent** with the ontological, theoretical and political approach of the whole project and with the changes made to the implementation. These adjustments were **inspired by epistemological debates on feminist situated knowledge**. This entailed reconsideration of the whole research process, objectives and our position as researchers, adapting the strategies employed to produce and disseminate knowledge, as well as the impact of our work on a society in which cis heteropatriarchal and racialized relations of power and dominance are present (Biglia and Bonet, 2017).

1.1 The objectives of the evaluation were:

1. To evaluate the training in terms of the **students and teaching and education staff's satisfaction** with the different elements of the **capacity building training**.

1.a To understand whether the participants' **sociodemographic characteristics affect** their **satisfaction** with the training.

2. To understand the **possible effects of the programs** (training and gamification) on **changes to opinions and awareness** of the prevention of male violence among students.

2a. To verify whether **combining the training with the gamification** has a **major effect** on improving students' awareness and attitudes towards GBV.

2b. To understand whether **active participation** in the training and/or gamification **makes students substantially more sensitive to GBV** than their schoolmates.

2c. To check whether **awareness** about the subject is **different depending on certain characteristics of the participants** (age, gender, sexual preference, etc.).

3. To understand whether **gamification has played a key role in fostering internalization of sensitivity towards GBV** and changes to the students' attitudes and behaviors.

1.2. Planned methodological procedure

To respect the **quasi-experimental approach** included in the original project, **three different schools** with different levels of implication had to be involved in each city:

Table 1. Schools' implication in the project

Case	Actions	Bcn	Mi	Ma
Intervention (Int)	Capacity Building Training + Gamification	Ba_Int	It_Int	Ma-Int
Semi-control (Sc)	Capacity Building Training	Ba_Sc	It_Sc	Ma-Sc
Control (Co)	No intervention is applied	Ba_Co	It_Co	Ma-Co

The **semi-control groups** were required in order for the Cut All Ties team to understand whether, and the extent to which, the combined effect of the training and gamification are more successful than training sessions alone.

IMPORTANT RECOMMENDATION: To be comparable, all of the schools need to be of very similar characteristics in terms of number of students; social-cultural-economic background; commitment of the school to the fight against GBV; student and teacher interest and attitudes in gender issues; hidden curricula; gender of students and staff etc.

In order to achieve the evaluation objectives, we designed a **multi-method approach** that would also allow us to **triangulate quantitative and qualitative information**. In the following table we present an overview of the instrument used for data collection and its relationship with the research objectives.

Table 2. Design of the evaluation

**In Spain these are third- and fourth-year bachelor students, in Italy these are students in the first and second year of High School*

Instrument	Obj.	Subject involved	Timing
Satisfaction surveys (1a & 1b)	1, 1a	Trained students and teachers	
Pre-awareness survey (2)	2, 2a,2b, 2c	All second grade* students at the 6 schools	course
Post-awareness survey (3)			Before any intervention When gamification ends
Focus groups (4a & 4b)	2b, 2c,3	Min. 2 with students & 1 with teachers per INC& SC school	After gamification, towards the end of the school year
Gamification record sheets and interview (5 & 6)	2c,3	Gamification trainers	During gamification and at the end

All of the information had to be obtained anonymously. Nonetheless, to compare students' changes of opinion it was necessary to have a **code** that allowed us to connect their surveys. Special attention was paid to guaranteeing that schools **did not have access to students' individual responses**. The anonymization protocol used for the survey is presented below:

PROTOCOL FOR ANONYMIZATION AND CODIFICATION OF THE SURVEY

Based on each class/school's registers in alphabetical order, a code is assigned to each student (this includes the city, type of school according to the intervention, year, class, student).

Questionnaires are prepared with the codes printed on all pages and put in alphabetical order.

Teachers hand out the questionnaires in that order and if anyone is absent, their questionnaire is left out.

After the questionnaire is completed, each student puts it in a sealed envelope. The envelopes are opened by members of the local project teams, who record the answers in a database provided by the evaluation team.

The questionnaires are kept in the custody of the CUT ALL TIES national teams, who are responsible for checking the quality of the records and for keeping them in a secure space to which the IET has no direct access.

When the results are disclosed, a different random code is associated to each response.

1.3. Ethical and methodological considerations for data recollection

The **ADB's Social Intervention Ethics Committee**, accredited as an Ethical Reflection Space (ERESS) by the Ethics Committee of the Social Services of Catalonia, oversaw the **ethics approval (ISO-9001)**. The Cut All Ties project coordinators obtained the approval of ethical consent of all the participants, and of their parents or legal guardians. Before starting the questionnaire, the students were reminded about the confidentiality of their information: neither their teachers, parents nor the school had access to their answers. The Cut All Ties team also reminded them that their participation was voluntary and that they were not obliged to complete the questionnaire once they had started it. Respondents were told that they could deposit their completed paper questionnaires in a sealed ballot box that could not be opened by the school staff. The project supervisors also oversaw the collection of the data and their storage.

The **IET is not responsible for data collection**. It is the partners and project supervisors who oversee the collection and storage of data, and ethical consent. However, the IET did design ethical recommendations to be implemented in the evaluation process, as presented below. Once the IET has received the anonymized data, its use and storage becomes its responsibility.

Satisfaction Questionnaires

- a. Provide participants with paper questionnaires that the trainers will register in a database.
- b. Issue the satisfaction surveys in the last session of the training course.
- c. Associate the same code to each students as allocated for the awareness survey. This code must be registered in the anonymous survey. Respondents should deposit their completed questionnaires in a closed box (similar to a ballot box) which cannot be opened by the staff of the center.

Awareness (pre and post survey)

- a. Do not give any information to students and teachers before the pre-test has been delivered.
- b. The survey should be administered at all schools in the same month.
- c. At each school the survey must be submitted to all students at the same time.
- d. Post questionnaires should be completed as late as possible to allow detection of the multiplicative effect of the gamification.
- e. Participants should be provided with paper questionnaires that the trainers register in a database.
- f. Link pre and post student questionnaires to assess trends.

Focus groups

The moderator plays a key role: this person does not intervene, but only raises the topic, stimulates discussion among the participants, and catalyzes the production of discourse by encouraging and controlling the flow of conversation while ensuring it remains on-topic. Participants will be asked for permission to record the sessions. All required information about the project will be given to the participants and the use of the information obtained from the focus groups will be explained. Participants will be asked to keep everything discussed during the focus group confidential. The anonymity of the participants will be maintained through the use of codes. All information that can recognize participants will be deleted. Moderators will make the transcripts of selected material in a record database provided by the evaluation team to avoid misinterpretations. The IET recommended that focus groups be held with 20% of the participants in both processes (training and gamification).

Gamification sheet and interview with trainers

This interview will be conducted directly by the IET team in the moderator's native language. Anonymity of participants will be guaranteed by observing the IET team's ethical code. The team will provide the trainers with the registration form. The IET recommends implementation of the gamification stage after issuing the satisfaction surveys. The registration form should be filled in after each challenge is created. The staff of the center should not have access to the information about the challenges. The gamification stage can only be carried out in Intervention (Int) centers.

2. Adaptation of the methodological approach

2.1. Incidences

This section highlights the **major deviations from the original plan of action** that had important consequences for the evaluation. In the following section, we will detail how **the evaluation plan was adapted to this**. However, we must highlight that the statistical results should be considered merely indicative because the variations and incidences corrupted their statistical validity.

General

- a. The **condition of having similar schools** in each city was **not met**.
- b. **Sample is not always homogeneous between** INT and SC schools.
- c. In **Madrid** there was **no control group**.
- d. The **timeline of the training** and other actions was **extremely different** from one school to another. For example, in Milan the training started later, and there was very little time for running the gamification part.
- e. In Milan, **the teachers** received **information** about the project **before the awareness pre-test** was submitted.
- f. In some SC, students **had access to information about the gamification process**. They were informed about the gamification features and possibilities and were given the opportunity to test the app. Italian trainers explained that in both the students' and teachers' training material, the presentation of the gamification was included in the last section, and was hence presented both at the INT and SC schools.
- g. In Milan, **the gamification process was not successfully implemented** while in Madrid and Barcelona **it did not have the expected impact in terms of student engagement**.

Training implementation

- a. In each city, trainers **made adaptations to the training contents and dynamics**, so the satisfaction survey is **not actually evaluating the same course**.
- b. For example, as explained in the interview, in Barcelona the trainers noticed **major refusal among the students** to address gender-based violence directly. The students acted aggressively and reluctantly towards the Cut All Ties team. Therefore, they **needed to adapt some contents of the training** and addressed the issue of GBV prevention through **sexual education**.
- c. Also, the **duration** of the training was **extremely variable among territories**, from three to ten weeks.
- d. Finally, **the composition of the trained groups varied a lot** due to the requirements of the high schools involved. For example, in the SC school in Madrid the training was carried out with students implicated in a pre-existing **feminist group**, and this led to the development of more dissemination strategies than at the INT school.
- e. In Milan, the trainers also faced much **resistance and confrontation**, but they decided to work with all the class groups **as programmed**. The trainers would like to have to **adapted the contents much more and especially the timing of the training**, but they felt they had to follow the agreements to be comparable between cities.

Satisfaction survey

- a. The satisfaction surveys were often **not implemented in the last session of the training**. The time elapsed between the end of the training and the distribution of the surveys may have led to specific memory loss.
- b. **Not all the participants were present when the satisfaction survey was delivered**. This implies that some samples were lost (particularly at some schools and in the sessions addressed at teachers).
- c. By the time the satisfaction survey was delivered at some INT schools **they had already started the gamification process**, creating data comparability issues.

Gamification

- a. The gamification **was implemented in diverse ways** and **moments** in each city.
- b. In Milan the app was **presented both at the Intervention and Semi-Control** schools, invalidating any further evaluation of the effect of gamification.
- c. **Very few students participated in the gamification**, hence there was insufficient data to perform the Bivariate analysis.
- d. In Milan, the **gamification was not implemented as successfully as expected** and very few challenges were created.

Awareness survey

- a. The awareness surveys were **not implemented at the same time** at all centers.
- b. Training started and finished with **months of differences** so its multiplicative effect is not comparable because the times between the delivery of the pre-test and post-test are so different.
- c. At some high schools the awareness survey was **not submitted at the same time** to all participants, which means some students already knew the questions before doing the survey.

2.2. Objectives (modified):

Due to the incidences and gaps in the gamification process (see section 4.4) the evaluation team redefined the following new objectives:

1. To assess the training through **student and teaching and education staff's satisfaction** with the different elements of the capacity building training.
 - 1.a To understand whether the **participants' sociodemographic characteristics affect satisfaction** with the training.
2. To find out the **possible effects of the training program** on changes in **opinion** and **awareness** about the prevention of GBV violence among students.
 - 2.c. To check whether **awareness** on the subject was **different according to some of the characteristics of the participants** (age, gender, sexual preference, etc.).
3. To understand whether **the training played a key role** in encouraging internalization of sensitivity towards GBV.

3. Data collection

3.1. Satisfaction survey

The evaluation team designed **two satisfaction surveys** (adapted from previous ones designed and tested by the IET and their teams in the GAPWork and USVReact EU projects): one for **teaching and education staff** (hereinafter, TES) and the other for the **students** who received the capacity building training.

The dimensions included were expectations and global evaluation; **contents, specific activities, and teaching; personal benefits** and the **quality and usefulness** of the course.

The following table shows the **sample for the evaluation survey of TES and Students**. As we can see, only 55% of TES filled in the survey, so the **sample is not significant**, while for **students it is significant** with a confidence level of 99% and an error margin of 5%.

Table 3. Satisfaction survey sample

	City	N	n	n (%)
TES	Milan	31	14	45
	Barcelona	14	10	71
	Madrid	15	9	60
	Total.....	60	33	55
Students	Milano	78	69	88
	Barcelona	48	32	67
	Madrid	32	28	88
	Total.....	158	129	82

DATA ANALYSIS

The following data analyses were conducted:

- **Descriptive and exploratory analysis.** To obtain an overview of the general evaluation of the training program.
- **Univariate and Bivariate analysis** (correlation analysis), to understand whether the satisfaction is related to the gender or city of the students, teachers, and education staff.
- **Comparative analysis** between groups (teaching and education staff/students).

4.2. Awareness surveys

All the items were designed from an **intersectional feminist perspective** and especially for young students (language and expressions, images, examples, etc.).

The first version of the survey was **evaluated by five experts in the methodology and gender related violence and five student peers**. Their comments were used to improve the final version of the survey in liaison with the IET and the Coordinators of this project.

In the following table we present an outline of the survey:

Table 4. Dimension of the pre/post-test survey

Dimensions	Information
Sociodemographic information	Gender identity; sexual orientation; feminist background
SGBV in relationships and sexuality among young people	Aggression; jealousy; loss of family and friendships; control of clothes and leisure activities; harassment; rape; passive-aggressive behavior; implicit threats; gaslighting; verbal abuse; isolating a person from family and friends; use of sex to achieve goals
Gender cyber violence	Mobile control; tracking apps (geolocation); spying on the phone and monitoring apps; social media control; abusive password control
Identification of SGBV	Active and passive role in aggression; SGBV in sexual-affective relationships; support for assaulted persons.
Perception of safety at the institute	Gender expression; personal and group support
Others	Definitions of SGBV; self-perception and SGBV

Not all of the pre-test participants were present in the post-survey. Hence, the IET only included in the sample those students who **answered both the pre- and post-test**.

Table 5. Awareness survey respondents and sample by center

Data set	N (total no. of students by type of center)	n (sample)*	Final sample
Int	2,192	328	485
Sc	1,882	320	487
Co**	1,582	310	313
Total.....	5,656	958	1,285

*Sampling error = 5%, confidence interval = 95%, p and q = 50%.

**There is not Co center in Madrid.

Table 6. Awareness survey respondents and sample by city

Data set	N (total no. of students by city)	n (sample)*	Final sample		
			Pre-test	Post-test	Sample
Milan	2,670	310	661	567	436
Barcelona	1,136	288	554	537	519
Madrid**	1,877	320	351	351	330
Total.....	5,656	918	1,566	1,455	1,285

Sampling error = 5%, confidence interval = 95%, p and q = 50%.

**There is no Co center in Madrid.

Data analysis

The IET **compared** the awareness of GBV **before and after the intervention** (capacity building training and gamification) using a median comparison test (Wilcoxon signed rank). The aim was to detect whether the **training and gamification led to any improvement in awareness about GBV**. Based on the characteristics of the data, a descriptive analysis was performed to verify the results of the statistical tests of median comparisons.

4.3 Focus Group

As explained earlier, the aim of the focus groups (FG) was to **understand whether the training fostered internalization of the content presented**. For

this purpose, the research team designed a script for the focus groups to **qualitatively evaluate the students' and TES' opinions about the impact of the capacity building training** and the **gamification** process.

The FG **were conducted by moderators** from each city and the participants were students and TES that took the training.

The IET suggested there should be **2 Focus Groups per center**, 1 with teachers and 1 with students. The sample was selected from among the participants (between 7 and 10 people per group, considering diversity and heterogeneity). The students needed to have participated in the capacity building training, or the gamification process, and the teachers had to be related to these specific students.

The **final sample per city** and **type of center** is shown in table 7:

Table 7. Focus Group Sample

Type of center	Participants	City			Total
		Milan	Barcelona	Madrid	
Int	Students	10	11	15	36
	Teachers	5	11	8	24
	Total	15	22	23	60
Sc	Students	12	24	13	49
	Teachers	5	6	1	12
	Total	17	30	14	61

The FGs were audio recorded, and **all the participants gave their informed consent.**

Data Analysis:

Thematic **categorical analysis** and **dominant narratives** were used for the analysis. The analysis included 4 phases:

Table 8. FG Analysis Phases

Phase	Analysis description
Reduction	Moderators transcribe and translate the most relevant citations in a coded document provided by the evaluation team.
Description	The coded information is organized
Comparison	Data obtained from different sources and instruments are related and correlated
Interpretation	Meaning is attributed to the information obtained, the study phenomenon is interpreted, and the results are issued.

The collected data was rather basic, so **it was not possible to make a comparison** between the focus groups in each territory. Instead, we decided to use it to **better understand some of the quantitative results**.

4.4. Gamification Sheets and Interviews with gamification trainers

With the aim of understanding the gamification process we prepared a sheet on which the **trainers** of the gamification activity **could note for each action implemented**:

- a. Name of the **challenge** and **description**
- b. **General information** about the challenge (including expectations and level of satisfaction)
- c. **Specific information** about the challenge (participation, the multiplicative effect of the actions and the theme of the challenge)

However, the gamification, as designed, **was practically unimplemented in Milan, while in Barcelona and Madrid** it did not achieve the expected engagement. Moreover, the challenges in these territories, which were mostly launched with the help of the trainers, received almost no response in terms of actions.

Table 9. General information

	Barcelona	Madrid
Challenges carried out	52	55
Average rate of responses (actions)	1.25	0

The individual and group interviews that we held with the gamification trainers from each city were supposed to qualitatively assess the gamification process. We decided to focus them on the challenges that arose in the gamification process.

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